

DOES FINANCIAL FLEXIBILITY ENHANCE THE PROFITABILITY OF MONEY DEPOSIT BANKS? EVIDENCE FROM NIGERIA

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ABSTRACT

This studied examined the effect of financial flexibility on profitability of Money Deposit Banks in Nigeria. The study adopted the survey method and data were collected using a structured questionnaire and these were complemented with oral interview. From a population of 694, a sample of 255 was selected through multi-stage sampling technique. The hypothesis was tested using the probability values anchored on simple linear regression estimations. The findings revealed that flexible financial practice in the firms studied has a positive effect on profitability (p -value = 0.000, $R^2 = 0.611682$). Based on the findings, the study concludes that financial flexibility enhances profitability of Nigerian Money Deposit Banks. Among others, it is recommended that an appropriate flexibility mix should be adopted by deposit money banks in order to increase and sustain the profitability of their firms.

Key words: Financial Flexibility, Profitability, Money Deposit Banks, Multi-stage Sampling

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1. INTRODUCTION

The banking sector reform as a part of the Federal Government economic repositioning took the players unawares. The reform popularly known as “bank consolidation” has as its important goal: the increasing of banks operational capital of N2 billion to a minimum of N25

billion. This was followed by a policy that banks must satisfy these new requirements by December, 2005[1].

The main goal of the restructuring is to guarantee an effective and strong financial system. The policies are designed to help the banking sector create the required backbone to support the economic development of the country by effectively carrying out its duties as the focal point of financial intermediation [2]. The key ingredients of the 13-point restructuring programme include minimum operational capital of N25 billion with a deadline of 31st December, 2005; consolidation of banking firms through merger and acquisitions; withdrawal of public sector funds from commercial banks beginning from July 2004, the establishment of an asset management company; and the establishment of the financial intelligence department.

Due to the restructuring, many Nigerian Money Deposit banks have adopted flexible financial practices, which they hope will help in enhancing their competitiveness in the industry, and consequently translate to higher profitability. Nevertheless, some of the banks still record low profits. Besides, there are cases of mergers and acquisitions among banks. For instance, in March this 2019, Diamond Bank of Nigeria merged with Access Bank of Nigeria. These and similar cases may prompt one to ask: does financial flexibility actually enhance profitability in Nigeria Money Deposit Banks? To answer this question, we hypothesize as follows:

Ha: There is a significant relationship between financial flexibility of Nigerian money deposit banks and their profitability.

Whereas [3] investigated the effect of financial flexibility on financial performance of some listed firms in Tehran, [4] investigated the relationship between financial flexibility and financial performance with the ratio of book value to market value in Tehran listed firms. Besides, many researchers had examined the direct relationship between labour flexibility and organizational performance [5], others on the effect of human resource flexibility on organisational performance [6]; and some others on the effect of external work flexibility, and internal work flexibility on the organisational performance [7]. Yet, none had investigated the effect of financial flexibility on profitability of Nigerian Money Deposit Banks. This study, therefore, is aimed at advancing the previous studies by conducting this investigation.

2. REVIEW OF LITERATURE

2.1. The Concept of Financial Flexibility

Financial flexibility is seen as ‘conserving debt capacity of a firm to make future expansions and acquisitions’ or ‘reducing interest responsibility, so that it does not need to shrink the business in case of an economic problem’ [8]. It is “the ability of a firm to approach and restructure its finance with low transaction costs”, to handle financial distress, and to fund investment at low cost when profitable opportunities arise” [9].

Several definitions of flexibility as explained in extant literature recognize the reactive or preventative nature of flexibility while neglecting the exploitative nature of flexibility for uncertain competitiveness or opportunities. The combination of preventive and exploitative nature of flexibility is seen by [10] who views flexibility in two different perspectives: internal flexibility as the firm’s capacity to adapt to the demands of the environment, while external flexibility as the firm’s capacity to influence their environment and thereby reduce their vulnerability.

Many of the decisions taken today in firms for the future can be risky. Eventually, maximizing the firm’s resource should be the main objective of optimizing financial flexibility. Accordingly, one may define financial flexibility as a firm’s ability to mobilize its

financial value in order to take preventive and exploitive actions in response to uncertain contingencies that may occur in the future in a timely manner.

Financial institutions hold excess liquidity to cope with the unpredictable nature of loss in order to accomplish a competitive advantage for high pricing and better margins [11].

2.2. The Life-cycle of Financial Flexibility

Financial flexibility refers to a survival and growth mechanisms which can be adopted by firms in a competitive business environment. According to our definition, firms with more growth opportunities relative to expected future cash flows need more financial flexibility than those with less investment opportunities relative to expected future cash flows. Also, firms with financial constraints need more financial flexibility than those without such constraints, *ceteris paribus*. In short, a balanced and integrated understanding of the effect of flexible financial decisions require a holistic view on (1) future growth opportunities, (2) financial constraints on raising additional capital, and (3) cash flows that will become available in the future. As a mode of providing such a holistic perspective, [12] identify three stages of a firm's life-cycle in its financial progress as follows: (i) a development stage, where the firm expects large future investment opportunities but low expected earnings in the foreseeable future with greater financing constraints; (ii) a growth stage, where the firm possesses many growth options, begins generating positive earnings with large expected cash flows in the foreseeable future, and faces less financing constraints; and (iii) a maturity stage, where the firm has declining growth opportunities, generates large current cash flows from assets in place but expects declining cash flows in the foreseeable future and faces little financing constraints.

The three life-cycle stages serve as reference points on the cross section of firms' desire for financial flexibility: firms in the development stage make financial decisions that provide the most flexible financial options; firms in the growth stage exercise currently available growth options with all available financial resources; and firms in the maturity stage focus on servicing debt and preserving some financial flexibility.

We rely on several firm characteristics to identify a firm's position across the life cycle of financial progress. We first consider earned capital as a proportion of total assets (or total equity) to proxy for the firm's financial life cycle. Earned capital is the accumulation of a firm's reinvested profits over time. Researchers like [13] argue that the mix of earned and contributed capital proxies a firm's financial life-cycle stage; i.e., firms with low earned capital relative to contributed capital tend to be in the capital infusion stage (the development stage), whereas firms with greater earned capital tend to be more mature with ample cumulative profits that make them largely self-financing (the maturity stage). Equally, we consider additional variables such as firm size, cash holdings, operating cash flows to value ratio, dividend payouts and long-term credit ratings as alternative proxies for the financial life cycle [14].

We measure firm size by net sales and total assets. Small firms are more likely to be in the development stage with many unsubstantiated opportunities but with less available funds than large firms. Small firms are also likely to have more constraints in having access to capital markets, causing them to concern for financial flexibility to cope with future contingencies. Large firms are often better diversified than small firms and have the inherent capability to endure future contingencies because each line of business represents an open option.

But large cash holdings incur higher costs: in addition to the opportunity costs forgone, they are exposed to a risk of inefficient uses when the firm does not have enough investment opportunities [15]. Thus, firms would balance the costs and benefits of holding cash. Since preserving financial flexibility through cash holdings is costly, firms will hold large cash only

if it is desired in order to deal with future financial obstacles or to capitalize on future opportunities. For firms in the development stage that have large future investment opportunities while having low internal funds and facing greater financing constraints, the marginal value of cash should be higher than for firms in the maturity stage that have less investment opportunities relative to internally generated funds while having easy access to capital markets. Consistent with this argument, previous studies find those firms with stronger growth opportunities, riskier cash flows, and more limited access to capital markets hold more cash.

Large dividend payouts serve as an empirical indicator of a mature firm as large dividend payouts are generally not feasible for firms in the development stage that have not attained high profitability. Also, firms that pay large dividends are expected to be more flexible than non-paying firms since they can generate funds at lower costs by reducing dividends when there are shortfalls in funds [13]. Additionally, [16] posit that financially constrained firms (like those in the development stage) have significantly lower payout ratios.

Firms in the development stage have no reputation (credit ratings) while firms build up better reputations as they progress into the growth and mature stages. Some researchers like [17],[18] use credit ratings as a measure of financial constraints or accessibility to debt capital. Overall, firms with a greater need for financial flexibility are characterized by low earned capital, small size, large cash holdings, no dividend payouts, low operating cash flows to value ratio and no credit ratings.

2.3. The Concept of Profitability

Profitability refers to the extent to which an activity yields financial gain or profit. It is a derivative of Return of Equity (ROE) of shareholders of the firms after meeting all expenses and taxes [19].

Studies on the determinants of the banking profitability can be categorized divided into two: the studies focusing on a specific country; and studies focusing on specific factors within a range of countries [20]. High profits lower risk in two ways and have the potential to douse the tensions that may arise from negative shocks. And the prospect of future profits restrains banks' risk-taking behavior as they have more "skin in the game." While the level of bank profitability is important for financial stability it matters greatly where a bank's profits come from (<https://blogs.imf.org/2019/04/30/bank-profitability-consider-the-source/>)[21].

2.4. Empirical Review

Researchers like [3] investigated the effect of Financial Flexibility and Financial Performance of the companies listed in Tehran Stock Exchange. To do this, 183 companies were selected using certain criteria. The data were extracted from financial statements and existent information in Exchange Hall of these companies in a 4-year period beginning from 2010 to the end of 2014. Panel data method was used to evaluate the model. Moreover, descriptive and deductive methods were employed to analyze the data. The results indicated that there was a significant relationship between leverage and liquidity ratio with financial performance of the companies accepted in Tehran Stock Exchange.

Similarly, [4] Zahra investigated the relationship between financial flexibility and financial performance with the ratio of book value to market value in Tehran listed firms. The authors selected 50 firms using specific criteria. Required data has been obtained from financial statements and current information of these firms in a 5 years period from 2009 to 2013. In this research, they used advanced method of generalized momentum (GMM) and estimated generalized least squares (EGLS) method to test hypotheses. The results show that

there is a positive and meaningful relationship between leverage ratio and liquidity ratio as criteria of measurement of financial flexibility. In addition, there is a negative and meaningful relationship between the rate of assets return and the ratio of book value to market value.

3. METHODOLOGY

3.1. Research Design

The study adopted survey research design using structured questionnaire to elicit responses from the respondents. This method is very appropriate because of the dynamic nature of the data.

3.2. Sample and Data collection

The sources of data for this study were primary and secondary sources. Data collected from full-time employees of the selected banks across the country were analyzed using E-view. Through purposive sampling technique, six banks out of twenty two were selected. The criterion for selection was based on those banks that are consistent in the publication of their annual financial statements up to 2017. These banks are: Zenith Bank, UBA Plc, Union Bank, First Bank, Access Bank and Guaranty Trust Bank.

From the six banks with a population of 674, a sample of 254 was selected through proportionate stratified random sampling technique. This step was taken to eliminate bias and ensures fair representation. Two hundred and fifty four copies of questionnaire were distributed to the sampled respondents, but only 241 were retrieved indicating 93.8% return rated. Before filling the questionnaire, the respondents were assured of absolute confidentiality and as such were requested to give honest answers. These steps, expectedly, reduced the possibility of their responses being subjected to social desirability and acquiescence biases [22].

3.3. Measures

Concerning the survey scale, the quantitative close-ended statements were scaled according to a Likert Scale which, as [23] explained, a technique designed to measure attitudes, typically using a continuum of “strongly disagree” to “strongly agree. This survey has a scale of five responses which are “strongly disagree (5),” “disagree (4),” “Undecided (3)” “strongly agree (2),” and “agree (1)” ; (See the questionnaire at the appendix).

The reliability was established using Cronbach’s alpha and it gave a value 0.83 which is satisfactory. The content validity of the instrument was established with the assistance of three bank employees and three lecturers at our university. Because of the homogeneous attribute of the sample, we aggregated the responses from the respondents, used the values obtained in our estimation.

4. RESULTS

Step 1: Restatement of the Hypothesis

Ho: There is no significant relationship between financial flexibility and profitability.

Ha: There is a significant relationship between financial flexibility and profitability.

Step 2: Presentation and Analysis of Result

Dependent Variable: PROFITABILITY

Method: Least Squares

Date: 07/15/19 Time: 19:55

Sample: 241

Included observations: 241

Variable	Coefficient	Std. Error	t-Statistic	Prob.
C	4.165906	3.381851	1.231842	0.2192
FINANCIALFLEXIBILITY	0.622225	0.032069	19.40296	0.0000
R-squared	0.611682	Mean dependent var		21.01245
Adjusted R-squared	0.610057	S.D. dependent var		81.25610
S.E. of regression	50.74070	Akaike info criterion		10.69960
Sum squared resid	615333.7	Schwarz criterion		10.72852
Log likelihood	-1287.302	Hannan-Quinn criter.		10.71125
F-statistic	376.4749	Durbin-Watson stat		1.836720
Prob(F-statistic)	0.000000			

Source: Author's Computation Using E-views

Model Line: $PRO = b_0 + b_1FINFLEX + U$

Regression Line: $PRO = 4.165906 + 0.622225FINFLEX$

Where; PRO = Profitability, FINFLEX = Financial Flexibility and U = Stochastic Error Term.

Step 3: Interpretation

It can be deduced from the regression table that there is a positive relationship between financial flexibility of the money deposit banks and their profitability. Profitability is predicted to be at 4.165906 when all the variables are held at 0. The coefficient of financial flexibility is estimated at 0.622225. This implies that for every unit increase in financial flexibility of the money deposit banks, profitability will increase by 0.622225 values. The result shows also that financial flexibility is statistically significant with p-value of 0.000 which is less than the critical value of 0.05. The adjusted R^2 which is the summary measure that tells us how well the sample regression line fits the data is 0.610057. This means that 61% of the variation in profitability was explained by changes in financial flexibility. The remaining 39% was explained by variables not included in the model. Based on the analysis, we reject the null hypothesis (H_0) and then conclude that there is a significant relationship between financial flexibility and profitability at selected money deposit banks.

4.5. Discussion of Findings

The findings show that financial flexibility has a positive significant effect on organizational profitability. This result implies that the more a firm is financially flexible, the more profitable the firm is likely to become. These findings are in agreement with the work of [3] which revealed that there was a significant relationship between financial flexibility and performance of companies at Tehran Stock Exchange. Also, our findings support the work of [4] which revealed that there is a positive and meaningful relationship between leverage ratio and liquidity ratio as criteria of measurement of financial flexibility.

However, our findings differ from that of [24] who stated that financial flexibility is not compatible with low cost strategies because resources and processes that create flexibility and increase variety may also require higher costs.

5. CONCLUSION AND IMPLICATIONS

This study investigated the effect of financial flexibility on profitability of Money Deposit Banks in Nigeria for a period covering 2008-2017. The result revealed a positive significant relationship between financial flexibility and profitability in the banks studied. Based on the findings, we proffer the following recommendations. First, an appropriate flexibility mix should be adopted by deposit money banks in order to increase and sustain the profitability of the firms. Second, money deposit banks have to carefully scrutinize the introduction of financial flexibility, otherwise they risk reducing costs in the short term but jeopardizing the development model in the longer term.

This study contributed to knowledge in terms of geography because of the findings being based in Nigeria which differ from climes where substantiated studies had been carried out. Besides, the study contributed to the existing empirical literature essentially because it specifically investigated the effect of financial flexibility on profitability of money deposit banks in developing countries like Nigeria. However, we suggest that other researchers should advance the work further by investigating the effect of Employee Polyvalence on Employee Productivity at Nigerian Money Deposit Banks.

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QUESTIONNAIRE

S/N	Financial flexibility and profitability	SA	A	UD	D	SD
1.	Financial flexibility in workplace is seen as a means to improve firm's competitiveness and strategic consistency					
2.	Through financial flexibility, the extent to which our organization can readily take exploitive, reactive and preventive actions have improved.					
3.	There is reduction in transaction costs thereby enhancing profitability					
4.	By minimizing our interest obligations, so that we do not need to shrink our business in case of an economic down turn, our organisation's profitability opportunities have risen.					
5.	We practice human resource flexibility and this helps us in achieving our set goals.					
6.	Our workplace environment is conducive for achieving our set goals.					
7.	Managers and workers relate well to achieve set goals.					
8	Hard working employees are promoted regularly so as to achieve more in future.					